

27 **Supplementary Methods**

28 **Study Population and Clinical Characterization**

29 We utilized UKB-PPP data connecting extensive plasma proteomic profiling with clinical
30 phenotypes.²⁵ We excluded 7,516 of 52,995 participants profiled via the limited Olink
31 Explore 1536 platform for comprehensive coverage. The study population was confined to
32 those profiled with the Olink Explorer 3072 platform.

33 Participants were classified as having CRS if they had at least one hospital diagnosis coded as
34 ICD-10 J32x (chronic sinusitis) or J33x (NPs). Individuals without these codes served as
35 controls. To rigorously account for potential confounders, we collected the following key
36 clinical covariates: demographic factors (age and sex), body mass index (BMI), smoking
37 status, and relevant comorbidities, including asthma (ICD-10 J45–J46) and atopic dermatitis
38 (ICD-10 L20). Systemic steroid use was recognized and managed as a covariate, and in
39 accordance with established protocols individuals administered oral glucocorticoids during
40 the evaluation were categorized as systemic steroid users.²⁶ We excluded 435 participants
41 lacking complete data on these covariates, resulting in a provisional cohort of 45,044 before
42 quality control. The cohort selection process from the initial proteomics pool to the final
43 analytical sample is depicted in Supplementary Figure S1.

44 The study complied with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Institutional
45 Review Board (IRB 4-2025-1529). Informed consent was waived due to the study's
46 retrospective nature, with data anonymized according to IRB-approved protocols.

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48 **Plasma Proteomics and Blood Profiling**

49 Plasma protein profiling was performed using the Olink Explore 3072 platform, a next-

50 generation sequencing–based proximity extension assay that enables the parallel
51 measurement of relative protein abundance.²⁷ The platform provides normalized protein
52 expression (NPX) values on a log₂ scale following central quality control and plate
53 normalization. We utilized the centrally processed NPX dataset from the November release of
54 the UKB-PPP. The final analytical panel comprised 2,923 protein markers with adequate
55 coverage across all the included batches.

56 In addition to proteomic data, we incorporated 61 routinely measured blood cell and chemical
57 traits (Supplementary Table S1), including full blood count parameters, liver and kidney
58 function tests, lipid profiles, inflammatory markers (e.g., C-reactive protein), and selected
59 hormones. These blood test measurements were analyzed in conjunction with the proteomic
60 panel.

61

62 **Data Preprocessing and Missing Data Handling**

63 Data preprocessing involved assessing missingness at both feature and participant levels.
64 Features with >50% missing values were excluded. For participant-level quality control, we
65 identified and removed 700 patients with >30.0% missing values from the combined dataset.
66 This rigorous filtering combined with the exclusion of participants with incomplete clinical
67 covariates yielded a final analytical cohort of 44,344 individuals. Because the distributions of
68 most proteins and blood markers were non-normal and right-skewed, feature-wise median
69 imputation was employed for the remaining missing values in the proteomic and blood
70 marker datasets.

71

72 **Differential Expression Analysis and Feature Selection**

73 To identify biomarkers associated with CRS, ordinary least-squares linear regression was
74 performed for each protein and blood marker. Normalized protein expression or blood marker
75 levels were modeled as a function of disease status, adjusting for age, sex, BMI, smoking
76 status, relevant comorbidities (asthma and atopic dermatitis), systemic steroid use and batch.
77 The coefficient for the disease term was interpreted as the adjusted log₂ fold change.
78 Significance was determined using the Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR)
79 procedure, and proteins were considered to be differentially expressed if $FDR < 0.01$. For
80 secondary exploratory modeling analyses, significant features were also retained as candidate
81 inputs for machine learning models.

82

83 **Pathway Enrichment Analysis**

84 To provide a biological context, we performed a pre-ranked pathway enrichment analysis
85 using the Gene Ontology Biological Process (GO:BP), Reactome, and Kyoto Encyclopedia of
86 Genes and Genomes (KEGG) gene sets.^{28–30} Genes were ranked using a metric that
87 combined the P-value and the sign of the log₂ fold change. For each pathway, a normalized
88 enrichment score (NES) and FDR-adjusted q-value were calculated to identify pathways
89 enriched among upregulated or downregulated proteins.

90

91 **Secondary Exploratory Machine Learning Analysis**

92 For secondary exploratory classification analyses, the dataset was divided into a training set
93 (80%) and a test set (20%), with preserved CRS prevalence. We evaluated five supervised
94 classification algorithms: penalized logistic regression, random forest, gradient boosting,
95 extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost), and support vector machine (SVM) with a radial basis

96 function (RBF) kernel. To address class imbalance, we applied class weighting for logistic
97 regression, random forest, gradient boosting, and SVM, and tuned specific hyperparameters
98 for XGBoost to optimize the performance for the minority class. Hyperparameter
99 optimization for each algorithm utilized a grid search alongside 5-fold stratified cross-
100 validation on the training dataset. Model discrimination was subsequently summarized in the
101 held-out test set using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC-AUC).
102 Model interpretation involved computing feature importance and SHAP (SHapley Additive
103 exPlanations) values to elucidate significant predictors. To assess the contribution of
104 proteomic data, we created two parallel feature sets for each algorithm: (i) a full feature set
105 including 46 CRS-associated proteins and 5 blood markers, and clinical covariates; and (ii) a
106 non-proteomic feature set with 5 CRS-associated blood markers and covariates excluding
107 proteomic variables. Both feature sets were utilized for model training with an identical train-
108 test split and preprocessing methodology, followed by ROC-AUC comparisons on the same
109 held-out test set.

Supplementary Figure S1. Flow diagram of cohort selection in UKB-PPP

Supplementary Figure S2. Differential plasma protein expression in CRSwNP and CRSsNP.
 Volcano plots comparing plasma protein expression between (A) CRSwNP (n = 402) and controls, and (B) CRSsNP (n = 323) and controls.

Supplementary Figure S3. Pathway Enrichment Analysis. Dot plot summarizing the pathway of proteins upregulated in CRS across GO Biological Process, Reactome, and Hallmark databases. The x-axis represents the normalized enrichment score (NES), and the dot size corresponds to statistical significance. CRS, chronic rhinosinusitis; GO, Gene Ontology.

Supplementary Figure S4. Exploratory classification analysis using machine learning models. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves comparing the performance of five machine learning classifiers—logistic regression, random forest, gradient boosting, XGBoost, and support vector machine (SVM)—on the training set (left) and the independent test set (right).

Supplementary Figure S5. Differential plasma protein expression in CRS patients without asthma. Volcano plot comparing plasma protein expression between CRS patients without asthma (n = 496) and control individuals.

Supplementary Figure S6. Differential plasma protein expression in asthma patients without CRS. Volcano plot comparing plasma protein expression between asthma patients without CRS (n = 4,246) and control individuals.

Supplementary Table S1. List of 61 routinely measured blood cell and chemistry traits.

Category	Sub-category	Measurement Traits
Hematology	Erythrocytes (RBCs)	Red blood cell count, Haemoglobin concentration, Haematocrit percentage, Mean corpuscular volume, Mean corpuscular haemoglobin, Mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration, Red blood cell distribution width, Nucleated red blood cell count, Nucleated red blood cell percentage, Reticulocyte percentage, Reticulocyte count, Mean reticulocyte volume, Mean spheroid cell volume, Immature reticulocyte fraction, High light scatter reticulocyte percentage, High light scatter reticulocyte count
	Leukocytes (WBCs)	White blood cell count, Lymphocyte count, Monocyte count, Neutrophil count, Eosinophil count, Basophil count, Lymphocyte percentage, Monocyte percentage, Neutrophil percentage, Eosinophil percentage, Basophil percentage
	Platelets	Platelet count, Platelet crit, Mean platelet volume, Platelet distribution width
Biochemistry	Liver Function	Albumin, Alkaline phosphatase, Alanine aminotransferase, Aspartate aminotransferase, Gamma glutamyltransferase, Total protein, Direct bilirubin, Total bilirubin
	Renal & Bone	Urea, Creatinine, Cystatin C, Urate, Calcium, Phosphate, Vitamin D
	Lipids & Glucose	Cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, LDL direct, Triglycerides, Apolipoprotein A, Apolipoprotein B, Lipoprotein A, Glucose, Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c)
Specialized	Hormones	Oestradiol, Testosterone, SHBG, IGF-1
	Inflammation	C-reactive protein, Rheumatoid factor

Supplementary Table S2. Differential plasma protein levels between CRS cases and controls in the UKB-PPP cohort.

Protein	Log2 FC	CRS (mean)	Control (mean)	P-value	FDR	Direction
MMP10	0.309	0.389	0.048	5.840e-37	1.705e-33	Upregulated
PRG3	0.203	0.244	0.003	1.356e-24	1.980e-21	Upregulated
PRG2	0.183	0.263	0.026	2.808e-19	2.655e-16	Upregulated
CST1	0.315	0.368	0.007	3.637e-19	2.655e-16	Upregulated
CLC	0.236	0.362	0.063	1.108e-17	6.469e-15	Upregulated
CCL26	0.233	0.363	0.062	5.043e-10	2.454e-07	Upregulated
CAPS	0.215	0.489	0.206	3.163e-09	1.319e-06	Upregulated
RNASE3	0.259	0.432	0.102	1.031e-08	3.763e-06	Upregulated
WFDC2	0.084	0.192	0.060	2.932e-08	9.512e-06	Upregulated
POSTN	0.077	0.082	0.006	1.160e-07	3.386e-05	Upregulated
TCN1	0.061	0.072	0.007	2.651e-06	6.452e-04	Upregulated
ADAM8	0.056	0.065	-0.000	2.467e-06	6.452e-04	Upregulated
CDCP1	0.101	0.198	0.046	3.026e-06	6.797e-04	Upregulated
TGFA	0.087	0.180	0.065	4.562e-06	9.515e-04	Upregulated
IL6	0.139	0.324	0.119	5.261e-06	0.001	Upregulated
SELP	0.105	0.148	0.017	8.071e-06	0.001	Upregulated
SCPEP1	0.082	0.145	0.037	1.400e-05	0.002	Upregulated
SIGLEC10	0.060	0.084	0.010	1.705e-05	0.003	Upregulated
GADD45GIP1	0.085	0.156	0.058	2.302e-05	0.004	Upregulated
SIAE	0.082	0.130	0.022	2.493e-05	0.004	Upregulated
PRR4	0.112	0.213	0.082	2.650e-05	0.004	Upregulated
ITGA5	0.043	0.060	0.005	2.924e-05	0.004	Upregulated
SIGLEC8	0.073	0.119	0.006	3.121e-05	0.004	Upregulated
LONP1	0.137	0.211	0.053	3.033e-05	0.004	Upregulated
SORT1	0.063	0.083	0.010	3.699e-05	0.004	Upregulated
PAPPA	0.078	0.125	-0.007	3.636e-05	0.004	Upregulated
SEMA4D	0.051	0.049	-0.006	3.753e-05	0.004	Upregulated
MECR	0.139	0.191	0.030	6.043e-05	0.005	Upregulated
NOS3	0.087	0.167	0.042	5.404e-05	0.005	Upregulated
NPPC	0.079	0.185	0.044	5.457e-05	0.005	Upregulated
PPIF	0.098	0.206	0.098	5.741e-05	0.005	Upregulated
IL2RA	0.067	0.127	0.029	5.853e-05	0.005	Upregulated
CCL5	0.170	0.134	-0.045	6.176e-05	0.005	Upregulated
HPSE	0.143	0.114	-0.043	6.655e-05	0.006	Upregulated
BPIFB1	0.105	0.090	-0.003	7.123e-05	0.006	Upregulated
MOCS2	0.100	0.161	0.041	7.884e-05	0.006	Upregulated
CD22	0.068	0.053	0.010	8.348e-05	0.007	Upregulated
CD40	0.080	0.155	0.054	8.645e-05	0.007	Upregulated
IL18R1	0.054	0.093	0.014	1.042e-04	0.008	Upregulated
ACOX1	0.078	0.115	0.028	1.139e-04	0.008	Upregulated
LILRA5	0.051	0.080	0.000	1.272e-04	0.009	Upregulated

OXCT1	0.101	0.162	0.046	1.281e-04	0.009	Upregulated
CD80	0.050	0.086	0.026	1.329e-04	0.009	Upregulated
CCL19	0.195	0.542	0.335	1.378e-04	0.009	Upregulated
TMPRSS5	-0.060	-0.088	-0.014	1.391e-04	0.009	Downregulated
CFH	0.033	0.044	-0.006	1.524e-04	0.010	Upregulated